

Loop stacks and $\mathbb{E}_\infty$ -spaces via display blocks

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Abstract

Let $\mathbf{L}\mathfrak{X}$ be a loop stack. In this paper, we investigate the connection between $\mathbf{L}\mathfrak{X}$ and commutative ring spectra. We dedicate chapter 4 to Kolmogorov spaces.

~ Chapters ~

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1. **KO-structure**
 2. **The Mapping Class Group**
 3. **Fine Sites which are Locally Smooth**
 4. **Kolmogorov Spaces**
 5. **Weakly Chained Spaces and Periodicity**
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0. Introduction

These are an outgrowth of some thoughts I had while taking notes on the works of Noohi and others. Much of the labor has been outsourced before me, and some of the topics touched upon are, at times (quite literally) only tangentially related.

So, what is this all about? Essentially, there are two interpretations.

The mathematical interpretation

There's no "one right way" to think about what follows. In a certain, very "loose" sense of the theory, we want to consider how quantum phenomena, such as discrete number fields, behaved as adic decompositions of more continuous loop spaces of higher co-cycles.

The physical interpretation

Physically, you can think of a boson-like field crossing itself an infinite number of times at a distinguished locus (typically the target of a curl), and this is essentially a loop stack of degree 1. Loop stacks of degree two or higher take place in certain alternate dimensions, determined by Bott periodicity.

Chapter 1 | KO-structure

Let $(\mathfrak{X}, \text{Hom}(\{*\}, \mathfrak{Y}))$ be a stack over **Top**. Call it $\mathfrak{Z}$. Let $\mathcal{A}$ be a compact topological space; further, let it be Hausdorff. Then, there is a mapping stack

$$\mathbf{Map}(\mathfrak{Z}, \mathcal{A}) \simeq \text{Hom}(\text{Hom}(\mathfrak{Z}, \mathcal{A}))$$

whose fibrations are 2-cells in the bicategory of topological spaces, and whose cofibrations all admit retracts into the presentable category $\mathbf{Stk}_{\text{MAP}}$ of mapping stacks.

Suppose that $\pi_k(\mathcal{A})$ is homotopic to $\mathbf{S}^1$. Then, by [Str], $\mathfrak{Z}$ forms a *loop stack*, and we write (in slightly modified notation), $\mathbf{L}^1\mathfrak{X}$. Assuming $\mathbf{L}^1\mathfrak{X}$ to have a fixed point, $\{*\}$, gives us an isomorphism

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{L}^1\mathfrak{X} &\simeq \mathfrak{X} \otimes \mathfrak{Y}(\{*\}) \\ &= \bigvee_{p+q=\{*\}} (\Sigma_n)_+ \wedge \Sigma_p \times \Sigma_q(\mathfrak{X}(p) \wedge \mathfrak{Y}(q)), \end{aligned}$$

which is a genuine symmetric ring spectrum [Sym] with a degenerate locus. We model the passage

$$\{*\} \rightarrow \mathbf{L}^1\mathfrak{X} \times \mathbf{LocSys}_{\Sigma}(\mathcal{A})$$

as the *Bousfield localization* of $\mathfrak{Z}$ over a trivial line bundle $\mathcal{L}$, with a Hopf fibration

$$\mathbb{E}_{\infty} \rightarrow \text{Re}(\mathbb{H});$$

where, essentially, $\text{Re}(\mathbb{H}) = \mathbb{R}/\mathbb{C} \setminus \mathfrak{Z}$. In the usual sense,

$$\text{Re}(\mathbb{H}) \rightarrow \mathfrak{Z} \simeq \ker(\mathbb{Q}) \rightarrow \text{coker}(\mathbb{Q}_p \cup \{*\})$$

is an isomorphism of schemes, and the braided étale morphism

$$\mathbb{H}_{\text{ét}} \rightarrow |\mathbb{H}_{\text{ét}}| > \mathbb{Q}$$

is representatively generated by the similitudes of the real portion of the hyperbolic space over which the loop stack is classified. Thus, by [Sym], we have the following isomorphism:

$$(\mathbb{H}_{\text{ét}})_{\text{SYM}} \widehat{\bigoplus} \text{sim}(\iota\lambda) = \text{Cl}(q+\iota\lambda),$$

where q and λ are relatively coprime, and where ι is the *weight* of the classifying stack over the symmetric ring spectrum. We write $q+\iota\lambda=p$, and conclude that $\text{Cl}(p)$ is a clifford algebra over a real Hilbert space.

Definition 1.0.1 Let $\widehat{H}$ be a $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -graded real Hilbert space, and λ an idempotent of arbitrary characteristic. A **KO-structure** on $\widehat{H}$ is a unique left action (of displays), $L^n\mathfrak{X} \star_{\phi} \widehat{H}$, which lifts from the Noohi class of topological stacks to the category of topological spaces via a restriction on a unitary ideal, ϕ_{α} .

In other words,

Definition 1.0.2. A **KO-structure** is a *forcing notion* on a symmetric ring spectrum Σ_{∞} , such that $\Sigma_{\infty} \rightarrow \Sigma_{\infty}$ is a basepoint preserving automorphism, and the Hurewicz compactification of $\Sigma_{\infty}^{\{*\}}$ is a

unique transcendental ordinal κ which is δ -small within the compass $\Omega_{\Sigma_{\infty}^{\{*\}}}^{\text{Grpd}}$.

Warning 1.0.3 It need not be the case that $\Omega_{\Sigma_{\infty}}^{Grpd}$ admits a groupoid presentation; merely, the category

of groupoids stratifies (through covering sieves) the modal boundary of the space of operators generated by ϕ_{α} . In other words, the space of functions $\mathbf{SFunc}(\Sigma_{\square})$, as a closed Borel subspace of some unspecified space in the category $\mathbf{Top}_{\Sigma}$, any is characterized by (ramified by) the class of pluripotent functions on idempotents, as display blocks.

Remark 1.0.4. It is indeed insufficient for our purposes to suggest that a display be treated as an ideal (in the category of commutative spectra); instead, we denote by $\mathbf{Com}_{\mathbf{B}}(\partial\phi_n)$ the unique analytic valuation corresponding to κ .

Write:

$$\mathbf{Com}_{\mathbf{B}}(\partial\phi_n): \kappa_n \dashv \dashv \kappa_m; m < n$$

for the restriction from the fundamental projector κ to the discrete (adic) valuation of the ring in which κ is a finite prime ideal. The *KO-structure*, in some other words, is the effective (higher étale) regulator which assigns, for every map in $\mathbf{Fun}(\mathbf{Com}_{\mathbf{B}}(\partial\phi_n), \kappa_n)$, a cohomotopy class

$$\mathbf{Coho}(\phi \oplus_{m,n} \Sigma^{m-n}) \simeq \mathbf{Hurewicz}.$$

This is promising, as every discrete geometric representation of a slice category of $\mathbf{Top}_{\Sigma}$ yields *at least* one compass over a space whose fundamental group is, in principle, computable.

Definition 1.1.1 Let C_n be the n th Chern class, and let χ be the unique character determining the function $f(\chi) \rightarrow C_{n-1}$. We will call a Serre fibration from $f(\chi-i) \rightarrow C_{n-1}$ an *admissible monic* if the corresponding additive function $f(\chi+i) \rightarrow C_{n+1}$ is a cofibration of equal characteristic and rank, where

$$\mathbf{Rank}(\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{n})) = (\chi + |i|)^{\dagger};$$

an admissible monic which is also epic shall be called a *Hurewicz isomorphism*.

Proposition 1.1.2 Hurewicz isomorphisms are Quillen equivalences of topological stacks.

Let $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{A}')$ be two compact, adic, and discrete topological spaces, and let $\mathbf{L}^n \mathfrak{X}$ be a rank n loop stack, such that

$$\mathbf{L}^n \mathfrak{X} = \mathbf{L}^{n-1} \mathfrak{X} \times_{\mathbf{L}} \mathfrak{X} \cup (\mathfrak{Y} \cup \mathbf{L}^{n-2} \mathfrak{X}) \times_{\mathbf{L}} \dots \times_{\mathbf{L}} \mathbf{L}^1 \mathfrak{X};$$

and let $\phi_{\alpha} \rightarrow \phi_{\beta} = \phi^b$ be a tilting (of displays). We see plainly that if $\beta = \alpha[r]$, then $\mathbf{Rank}(\phi_{\beta})$ is equal to or strictly lower than $\mathbf{Rank}(\phi_{\alpha})$, and we define $\mathbf{Rank}(\phi^b)$ to be the arithmetic difference between them. If r is polar, and Abelian, then there is a canonical isomorphism

$$(\mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A}') \rightarrow \mathbf{L}^n \mathfrak{X},$$

where n is equal to the sum of roots of unity of $\mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{A}'$. If $\mathbf{L}^n \mathfrak{X}$ is cohomologically affine, then the pole $\mathbf{r}^{\pm 1}$, and further it is preserved by any orientation-preserving mapping $\mathcal{A} \times \mathbb{S} \times_{\mathbb{S}} \mathcal{A}' \mapsto \mathbb{R}\mathbb{P}$. That is to say, if $\mathbf{D}_{\mathbf{Mod}}$ is a Dieudonné module acting on the orbits of either of $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{A}'$, then there is a unique Hurewicz isomorphism generated by the displays of $\mathbf{D}_{\mathbf{Mod}}$, which is a delooping of the unitary fiber strata of the underlying compact space.

Proposition 1.1.3 For a loop group $\mathbf{LG}(\lambda)$, there is at least one lifting $L\tilde{G}(\lambda) \rightarrow \mathbf{L}^n\mathfrak{X}$, such that the summand of complete kernels $\sum_{k=0}^n \xi_k$ is maximally degenerate.

Proof We borrow in large part from [Win]. Let $\mathfrak{o}(\sum_{k=0}^n \xi_k)$ be a discrete valuation, and $\mu_{p,q}$ be a nilpotent cocharacter of λ . Then, for left (resp., right) action on λ , there is a unique right (resp. left) *earthquake* $\mathcal{E}$ such that $\mathcal{E}:\xi_k \rightarrow \mathcal{P}$ is a non-singular locus for the lifting from the adic space to the trivial Banach space. Thus, assuming k to be a natural number, $\text{inf}(k)$ is equal to one, and therefore there is always one such lifting.

Remark 1.1.4 Assume that the lifting is faithful; then, the flat embedding of the nilpotent display over λ , $emb:\lambda_{\text{nilp}}^b \rightarrow \mathbf{L}^n\mathfrak{X}$ is *fpqc*. This morphism is essentially an earthquake with some additional data; for instance, the tangent varieties of the tautological line bundle over $\mathcal{E}$ are considered (as a stack of presheaves) to be Cauchy.

Lemma 1.1.5 Let Y be a quasi-projective A scheme, with A a ring. Assume that A is noetherian, and $\mathfrak{a}$ -adically complete, for any ideal $\mathfrak{a}$. Then, the canonical map

$$Y(A) \rightarrow \lim_{\leftarrow n} Y(A/\mathfrak{a}^n)$$

is a Hurewicz isomorphism.

Proof That the map is a bijection was proved in [Win], pg. 7. That it is Hurewicz follows from embedding $Y(A)$ flatly in the category of commutative ring spectra.

Proposition 1.1.6 Let the above isomorphism be an isomorphism of schemes. Then, for any ideal $\mathfrak{a}$, there is a smooth embedding $\mathfrak{a} \hookrightarrow \text{rep}(\mathfrak{a})$.

We will identify $\text{rep}(\mathfrak{a})$ with a section of the tangent bundle over $\text{spec}(\mathbb{E}_\infty)$. Thus,

Proposition 1.1.7 For n pointwise additive segments of the line bundle $\mathbf{Bun}_\mathcal{A}$, where $\mathcal{A}$ admits stratification into sheaves p and q , one has a unique fixed point $\{*\}$ such that the n th Chern class C_n admits isomorphism after a blowup.

Proof Let $\widehat{p \otimes q}$ be a half-twist of objects in the vect-enriched category of sheaves. Let $\mathfrak{h}$ be a **Hopf** algebra. One has:

$$p[q] + q[p] - (p+q) \mapsto \mathfrak{t},$$

where $\mathfrak{t}$ is a torsor such that $\mathfrak{t}^{p+q}$ forms an ideal of some ring $\mathcal{O}$. We define $\mathcal{O}$ to be an overring admitting a Prüffer extension $S_{\text{ext}} \subset \mathcal{O}$.

Suppose that there is a display block $\mathbf{B}_\phi$ over $\mathbf{LocSys}(\mathcal{A})$. Then, we decompose into finite and tempered strata, $\mathcal{I}_1, \mathcal{I}_2, \dots, \mathcal{I}_n$, such that $\widehat{p \otimes q}$ yields a profinite surjection into the Witt group W_k . Let G be the Grassmanian of W_k . Then, there is a G -vector

$$\vec{G} = \lim_{k \rightarrow n} \ell_k$$

such that $\vec{G} \rightarrow \{*\}$ is an admissible monic.

Remark 1.1.8 See [T.D.], remark 2.3 for a slightly more involved construction. We identify some strata with the zero section of the vector bundle therein mentioned, and we replace $\mathfrak{h}$ with a generic s_0 algebra to provide the necessary ingredients. Then, we see that $\vec{G} \widehat{\otimes}_{\ell} \kappa$ is a crepant resolution over

MfldB $_{\phi}$.

Chapter 2 | The Mapping Class Group

Let $\text{MC}(\mathbf{Top}_{\Sigma})$ be the mapping class group for some topological space. Let $\text{Aut}(\text{MC}(\mathbf{Top}_{\Sigma}))$ be the set of all automorphisms of this group. Then, we are afforded a unique Nisnevich transfer

$$\mathcal{A}(\Sigma, \text{MC}(\mathbf{Top}_{\Sigma})) \rightarrow \mathbf{Top}_{\Sigma};$$

assume that the target is locally commutative. Then, one obtains a simplicial complex

$$\tilde{\Delta} = \Omega_{\Sigma}^{\infty},$$

which is a rough approximation of the loop group centered about a distinguish point whose stabilizer lies in Σ . As we have seen previously [Dis], we can easily assume that $\tilde{\Delta}$ is a *curve complex*; this allows one to visualize the map as a *real locus-preserving* fibration of the canonical Teichmüller space, $\mathbf{T}_g$. We have the isomorphism:

$$\mathcal{C}(S) \simeq_{\text{HUR}} \tilde{\Delta}_i$$

in the category of simplicial complexes, and by decomposing either side, one obtains a miniscule cocharacter μ_i . Thus, one obtains a (μ_i, λ) -display, ϕ_i , which acts by homothety on the spaces encompassed by $\Omega_{\tilde{\Delta}}^?$. Here, we have left the supremum of the compass undefined so as not to restrict ourselves necessarily to the case of finite complexes. Indeed, in an $\mathbb{E}_{\infty}$ case, one may seemingly want to leave open the possibility that the closure of the system is undefined. Thus,

$$\overline{\Omega_{\tilde{\Delta}}^?} = \lim_{i \rightarrow \infty} \delta_i,$$

for a δ_i -small component of any atlas over $\mathbb{E}_{\infty}$, there is a Bousfield localization which transforms the i -truncated space into a simple stratum, call it σ . By adjoining finitely many of these σ together, one obtains a ramshack Tits building, where every $\sigma_j \subset \sigma_i$ forms a unique system of alcoves, or an apartment. We let

$$\lim_{\leftarrow} i = j^{\pm},$$

so that the charts of the apartments conform to the polarity of the global (supposedly isotropic) space of holomorphic functions.

Thus, for any set $f(z)$ of harmonic functions over a potential well, there is at least one *real locus* r , which is the Cartier divisor in the Dirichlet boundary equation:

$$\lim_{z \rightarrow n} f(z) = \int_0^n \sum_z z_i r;$$

Here, we take this equivalence to be an equivalence of spectra. Thus, we rewrite it as:

$$\text{spec}(\lim_{\sigma \rightarrow \sigma'}) = \partial \Omega_{\sigma, \sigma'}^{\tilde{\Delta}} = \text{patch}(\phi_i).$$

Notice that the time-evolved equation exhibits a reduction in the number of degrees of freedom. This may be to our advantage in some cases, for example, when studying the purely categorical properties of Hermitian spaces. However, one still yearns for a more analytic scenario. Let

$$\text{fib}(\sigma) \rightarrow \delta_i \text{cofib}(\sigma')$$

correspond to some polynomial function $(f(z))^k + f(z)$, and let its zeros be defined. Set

$$S = \int_0^k (f(z))^k - \int_0^z f(z);$$

we define the *genuine étale spectrum*, $\text{Sp}_{\text{ét}}(\tilde{\Delta})$ of a simplicial complex as follows.

Definition 2.0.1 Let $\mathbf{X}$ be a $\mathfrak{b}$ -adically separated, quasi-projective variety. Let $\mathfrak{n}$ be a nilpotent character. We define the genuine étale spectrum as

$$\lim_{\rightarrow} S|_{\mathfrak{n}}$$

such that there is some shtuka for which the display $\phi_i: S \rightarrow S|_{\mathfrak{n}}$ is *complete*, stationary, and preserves chirality and polarity.

Remark 2.0.2 We define a map $\mathbf{T}_g \rightarrow_{\text{Sp}_{\text{ét}}} \mathbf{T}_g$ to be a real-locus preserving Satake equivalence. Let $\mathbf{E}$ be a section of an $\mathbb{E}_{\infty}$ manifold. Then, assuming $\mathfrak{n}$ commutes (up to homotopy) with smash products, the *real Lie group* $\mathbf{L}_{\mathfrak{n}}$ effectively generates the genuine étale spectrum of $\mathbf{T}_g$ and its geometric representations. ϕ_i functions as an operad, taking left-exact ring spectra to their tightly laced loop groups.

Proposition 2.0.3 Let $\overline{\Omega}_{\Delta}^?$ be a compass, and $\overline{\Omega}_{\Delta}^? \rightarrow \text{MCG}(\mathbb{O})$ a morphism to the mapping class group of octonions. Then, $?$ is defined by the formula

$$? = 2\mathfrak{I} + \mathbb{H}$$

Proof Since $\text{sup}(\overrightarrow{\mathbb{O}}) = \omega_{\lambda}$, we have that if κ is transcendental over $\mathbb{H}$, then $\omega_{\lambda} > \kappa$. Thus, $\omega_{\lambda} \vdash \mathbb{H} \cup \kappa$. Since $\dim(\mathbb{O}) = 2\dim(\mathbb{H})$, we have that $\mathfrak{I}\dim(\mathbb{O}) = 2\mathfrak{I}\dim(\mathbb{H})$.

We write the display block $\mathbf{B}_{\mathbb{O}}$, and denote its poles by $\mathbb{b} = H_{\bar{w}}^{-1}, H_{\bar{w}}$, where $H_{\bar{w}}$ is the Weyl module of highest weight, and we have

$$\mathbf{Com}_{\mathbb{b}}(\partial\phi_n) = \mathbb{b}^+ \cdot \mathbb{b}^- = \{*\},$$

giving us the unique exact point established earlier. Thus,

Theorem 2.1.1 There is a based point in $Top_{\Sigma}^{\{*\}}$ which is bipolar with respect to some octonionic manifold $Mfld_{\mathbb{O}}$.

Proof Denote by $\Phi_{L^n_{\mathfrak{X}}}$ the n-adic loop stack display of $\mathbf{B}_{\mathbb{O}}$. We must show that $\Phi_{L^n_{\mathfrak{X}}} : \overline{\Omega_{\Delta}^?} \rightarrow \Omega_{\mathbb{b}}^{\mathbb{O}}$ is a Quillen equivalence in the category of hyperbolic spaces.

Denote by $\tilde{\Delta}(N)$ the N-skeleton of the underlying simplicial complex. We first establish an admissible monomorphism

$$\tilde{\Delta}(N) \rightarrow \mathbb{b};$$

up to some notion of cohomological coherency, we define a maximally flat immersion of scenes

$$\text{SCENE}_{\tilde{\Delta}} \hookrightarrow \mathbb{O}|_{\mathbb{b}},$$

and we define a descent of étale schemes such that there is a long exact sequence

$$\mathbb{O}|_{\mathbb{b}} \rightarrow \mathbb{O}|_{\mathbb{b} + \kappa} \rightarrow \mathbb{O}|_{\mathbb{b} + 2\kappa} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \mathbb{O}|_{\mathbb{b} + \omega_{\lambda}\kappa}.$$

We let this be an isotonically descending chain with the fusion rule $\omega_{\lambda}\kappa = \kappa^{-\lambda}$, and we call it the *Kan coherent nerve* of the skeleton. We have that, if $Mfld_{\mathbb{O}}$ is quasi separated, then the Kan coherent nerve perfectly splits the space into left- and right-strata at the double point $\mathbb{b}$. Thus, by writing $\mathbb{b}$ as the compactification of a Lie group, we have that it is a δ -small vector space, and so it is easily seen to be coherent. In eight dimensions, one has that the $H_{\mathbb{W}}^-$ -modules are spectrally divergent, and so with an induced Kähler metric ϱ , we get the map

$$\varrho(\text{KNerve}_{\text{Coh}}) \rightarrow \mathbb{O}/2.$$

Lastly, we introduce a $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -grading and integrate over the structure sheaf $\mathfrak{F}_{\tilde{\Delta}}$ to obtain

$$\int_{\kappa} \mathbb{H} + 2\mathfrak{F} = \mathbb{O};$$

by loop group equality of $\mathbb{b}^{\pm} \sim \text{sup}(\mathbb{O})$, one obtains the desired result.

Q.E.D.

Proposition 2.1.2 If Λ is the *Novikov ring*, then $\mathbf{B}_{\mathbb{O}}(\Lambda_q^r)$ defines a cohomology class over some octonionic manifold which inherits its singularities from an effectively lensed scene $\mathcal{S}$. In particular, if φ is a free ideal of Λ , then there is a bijection between elements bounded by $\partial\varphi$ and units of $\mathcal{S}_r$, so that

$\sum_{\partial\varphi} \mathcal{Z}(B_{\mathbb{O}})$ is a complete orbifold, whereby an orbifold we mean a Deligne-Mumford stack over $\mathbb{C}$.¹

¹ See [QC]

Definition 2.1.3 Following [gms], with slight variation: a morphism $f: \mathcal{D} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ of (Artin) stacks is *cohomologically affine* if:

- f is quasi-compact
and
- the functor $f_! : \mathrm{QCoh}(\mathcal{D}) \rightarrow \mathrm{QCoh}(\mathcal{Y})$ is *exact*.

If $\xi \in \mathcal{D}$ is a finitely presented slice category admitting a cohomologically affine functor $f : \xi \rightarrow \xi'$, then the localisation to a small site over ξ' is an isomorphism of ind-schemes if and only if ξ is open. Further, if f is a Quillen equivalence², and there is a degenerate real locus θ of ξ , then there is an exact functor $t: (\xi, \xi') \rightarrow \mathrm{Top}_\Sigma^{\{*\}}$ such that $\theta \cup \{*\}$ is an idempotent of the field represented by Σ . Whence $\mathrm{Top}_\Sigma^{\{*\}} \simeq \mathbb{A}_\infty^{\{*\}}$, t is a Hurewicz cohomologically affine immersion of charts.

A slight variation is to say that if $\tilde{\Delta} \rightarrow \Sigma_\infty$ is *exact*, then the nilpotent display block $B_\infty^{\phi_\Sigma}$ is cohomologically affine.

If ρ is a cohomologically affine functor $X \rightarrow Y$, and the natural map $\mathcal{O}_Y \rightarrow \iota_* \mathcal{O}_X$ is an isomorphism, then, we shall, following [gms], say that that $\hat{\rho}$ is a “good moduli space.” Much can be said about good moduli spaces.

Proposition 2.2.1 If $\hat{\rho}$ is a good moduli space, and $\mathbb{A}^0$ is a distinguished ε -ball, then

$$d(\hat{\rho}, \varepsilon^*) = \hat{\rho} \sqcup \mathbb{A}^0$$

is also a good moduli space.

Proposition 2.2.2 Let $\mathcal{C}$ be a commutative ring spectrum. If, for any immersion

$$\eta: \mathcal{C} \hookrightarrow \mathcal{C}(S)_{\mathrm{DISC}}$$

the functor η is cohomologically affine, then η is a good moduli space.

Proof Let $\mathcal{C} = \mathbb{E}_\infty$ be an object in $\mathrm{Top}_\Sigma^{\{*\}}$. We denote by $\{*\}$ the distinguished basepoint of $\mathbb{A}^0$. Then, one has

$$\eta \sqcup \{*\}$$

is a good moduli space. Therefore, $\mathcal{C}(S)_{\mathrm{DISC}}$ is δ_i -small in the compass Ω_η^∞ , and so for a display block $\mathbf{B}_\eta$: $\phi_\eta \rightarrow \mathcal{C}(S)$, the associated fiber bundle $\mathbf{Bun}_\mathbf{B}$ is encompassed by a good moduli space.

Question What are examples of good moduli spaces for $\mathbb{O}$?

Chapter 3 | Fine Sites which are locally smooth

Let $\mathbb{k}$ be a complete, essentially perfect field, and $\overline{\mathbb{k}}$ be its $\mathfrak{b}$ -adic closure. Let N be a Noohi group. Then, one obtains

² More specifically a Hurewicz isomorphism

We identify t as the “Noohi torsor” of the (nucleus) of a system of holomorphic equations. There are a fair number of variations on the standard birational form of t , notably having an inclusion by co-cycles in $\text{LocSys}(\tilde{\Delta}\mathcal{C}(S))$.

3.1 Polarity as a Cocycle Completion

For a map

$$\text{LocSys}(\simeq(\bullet)),$$

given profinite access to presentation, the unitary iso-locus of the Cartesian-complete class of kernels exhibits zero ramified cokernels.

Definition 3.1.1 Trivial Completion

A small map of topological stacks $\mathfrak{X} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ is said to be trivially complete, if for every bijective Serre fibration, there is a δ_i -truncated retract to a class of coherent animas.

Example 3.1.2 If $\text{LocSys}(\mathbb{C}f(z))$ names an effective character class, then the tautological cofibration

$$\ell(\mathfrak{X}) \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}_n$$

is equivariant by $\mathbb{A}_\infty^*(*)^P/P_{nn}$.

Definition 3.1.3 If $*_\infty \rightarrow_{\text{Hur}} \mathbb{I}_n$ is a trivial fibration, and the op-map is complete, we say the mapping stack $\mathbb{M}_{ST}$ is *genuinely complete*.

Definition 3.1.4 If $(O \rightarrow B) \simeq P$ is an effective opfibration of pluripotent characters, we call its classifying stack “fundamental.”

Warning 3.1.5 The fundamental classifying map

$$\mathbf{P}^{\text{op}} \times \mathbf{P} \simeq \mathbb{P}_n; \lim_{\leftarrow} n/k \simeq \mathbb{Z}/2$$

is presentable and quasi-coherent in the étale site, but perfectly amenable to the Zariski site. Recall that, from strictly coarser (“better”)³ site for varying degrees of globalization, we have

$$\mathbf{Zar} \supset \mathbf{Nis} \supset \text{ét}$$

³ For the sake of cohomology

so the enriched fiber complex over each is generated by a chromatic number of strictly decaying strength. Thus, if density is preserved in each, assuming a constant number of n -cells in each, a lesser number in the degenerate Zariski set of places than in the genuine étale site is measured. If, by a Hausdorff dimension, we mean a strictly increasing adherence to coherency, we find it in the inverse strictly increasing opposite po-chain; thus **(eq. 3.2.0)**

$$\mathbf{D}_{\text{HAUSS}} \propto \mathbb{B}^{-n},$$

where $\mathbb{B}$ is the radius of an open ball in a slice category of Sites.

Proposition 3.2.1 For every simplicial complex $\tilde{\mathbb{C}}$, the co-skelata in stacks $\mathcal{S}$ are coprime to the additive metric on a $\mathbf{BG}_\infty$ space.

A proof would be very tedious to compute, but would likely involve a probabilistic measure of cozfine modules over Banach spaces. There are certain spectra for which the effective lensing of miniscule cocharacters (coweights) diverge absolutely as a result of certain braiding under qualitatively distinct fusion, weight, or tameness metrics. Thus, for a Θ link $\Theta^\pm \rightarrow \mathbb{C}_n$, the resulting divergent energy numbers are locally, but not typically globally, homogenous chambers of ε -chains.

Proposition 3.2.2 Given any effectively lensed space, $\mathcal{A}_{\text{LENS}}$, there is a chromatic measure (of charts) which is regulated by some path space⁴ $\mathcal{P}$, which is fiberwise directed and oriented towards the polarity of a miniscule co-character.

Proof Let $P_n \rightarrow_p \mathbb{P}(-)$ be an affine blowup of stacks. Let σ be the centralizer of P_n . Then, there is some opfibration⁵ $\varphi(-^*)$ which is regular, assuming the F-crystal of $\mathbb{P}(-)$ to be a regular set of displays.

Chapter 4 | Kolmogorov Spaces

Definition 4.0.1 A *Kolmogorov space* $\mathbf{K}$ is a pseudo-convex locally Hausdorff space with an exit path map $\mathbf{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$.

A Kolmogorov space is a specific entity, which exhibits a somewhat weaker property than $\mathcal{C}$ -infiniteness. A Kolmogorov space is a *set* $\mathcal{S}$ with extension e , transforming the base into a stable and uniform variety. We refer, instead of *affine* to the transformations of ordinary objects in Kolmogorov space as *subfine*. Simply, for any two objects $\mathbf{o}_1, \mathbf{o}_2$ and a split morphism $\mathbf{i}: \rightarrow$ between them, we label the above morphism $\mathbf{t}_1$, and the below $\mathbf{t}_2$, and their hypothetical composite is a **doubly bijective** morphism in the category of schemes. We equip each of $\mathbf{t}_1, \mathbf{t}_2$ with a pseudoscalar $\hat{s}$ and write $\hat{s} + d\varepsilon$ for the algebroid operator acting on (again, the nucleus of) a heterogenous spectral scheme.

We can put all of the infimums to one side (i.e., the zero object of each of $\mathbf{t}, \mathbf{o}$, or in a more generalized variety $\mathbf{m}$ as a k -tuple, and the supremums to the other and denote by $\mathbf{B}$ the first set and $\mathbf{B}^\#$

⁴ Not necessarily looped

⁵ Most notably a *lens fibration*

the second. The Θ -link (of Hodge modules) acts via a perverse sheaf $\mathcal{A}$, and has as its nerve $\tilde{\Delta}$. For each vector-like unit in the spectral realization of $\tilde{\Delta}$, there is an equipotent morphism of schemes into the stabilizers (as prime ideals) in $\mathcal{A}$.

$$(\tilde{\Delta}\delta_i \rightarrow \mathcal{A}\mathbb{I}) \simeq S_e \rightarrow S_e'$$

Yields the appropriate localization to spaces which should be⁶ loose $\mathbb{A}_\infty$ -spaces. Thus, we recover, from the triangulation at the beginning of **chapter 3**, a specific Bousfield localization of torsors into the D-brane potential of an arbitrary stable function.

We call a Kolmogorov space S_e' *more granular* than a cousin space S_e if its Tychonoff measure $\mathbb{t}_e$ consists of a greater probability space for the realization of relatively coprime projectors. Every map of Tychonoff measures is a map of display blocks, whence all of the displays are complete Hermitian, and in some other cases.

Proposition 4.1.1 An earthquake on a Kolmogorov space is a map of displays (as charts):

$$\phi_n \circ \phi_{n\pm q}^{-1}$$

which is equivalent to a small display block $\mathbf{B}_q$ in the category of schemes.

Remark The less granular case results from the additive operation, and the more granular case the subtractive. Intuitionistically, the additive operation is more precisely a *left earthquake* in a positively polarized regime; the *right earthquake* is the dual construction.

Conjecture The EPR bridge $\mathbf{B} \rightarrow \mathbf{B}^\#$ is a map from a fiber bundle to its associated tangent bundles.

Sk. of Proof Suppose $\mathfrak{K}$ to be a $\mathfrak{b}$ -adically separated field. Then the completion of the two-fold map $\mathfrak{K} \rightarrow \overline{\mathfrak{K}}_2$ is mutually orthogonal with the kernel $\mathfrak{K}^{-1}$

This is a valid condition in even numbers of dimensions with odd codimension. We represent $\mathfrak{K} \rightarrow \overline{\mathfrak{K}}_2$ by $\mathfrak{K} \rightarrow 2\mathfrak{I}\mathfrak{K}$.

Remark For Hermitian immersions, one has the reduction $\overline{\mathfrak{K}} \rightarrow 2\mathfrak{I}^\dagger\mathfrak{K} = 2\overline{\mathfrak{K}}$.

Proposition 4.1.2 A map into a “more granular” Kolmogorov space from a good moduli space has an increased Hausdorff dimension.

Proof See eq. 3.2.0; letting $\mathbb{B}$ be the fineness of the space, one has that the pullback space

$$\mathbf{Proj}_{\leq 2\mathfrak{R}}^{-n \infty \mathbb{B}} \mathcal{C}(\mathfrak{S})_{\text{SCENE}}$$

yields a greater number of fractional epics, and is therefore higher in Kolmogorov complexity, as determined by Hausdorff dimension.

Remark This is tantamount to saying that, as we zoom in on a Kolmogorov space, we observe, in some sense, “spikier” stacks than we would in the typical Hilbert space of a curve complex.

Proposition 4.1.3. For Hurewicz isomorphisms of the aforementioned pullback space, n is constant.

⁶ Or ought to be

Remark This amounts to saying that, for an “ideal isomorphism,” we are always *really* interested in the equivalences of *site*. The site is the projector of the Hausdorff dimension in any effectively lensed scene.

Let $\mathbb{E}$ and $\mathbb{F}$ be two complete algebraic fields with geometric representation in the category of stacks. For a looped stack $\mathbf{L}^n \mathfrak{X}$, the simplicial realization, $\tilde{\Delta}:(\mathbf{L}^n \mathfrak{X})^\circ$ in the category **SSets** is *equivariant* with respect to the underlying loop space if they are of the same rank, degree, dimension, etc.; we say that these properties are all preserved if

$$\{\mathbf{D}_{\text{HAUS}}(\tilde{\Delta}:(\mathbf{L}^n \mathfrak{X})^\circ) \mid \Omega_{\Delta}^n | \Omega_{\Delta}^n(\mathbf{A}_{\text{LENS}}) = \tilde{\Delta}:(\mathbf{L}^n \mathfrak{X})^\circ\}$$

is constant and locally constant across all slice categories of **SSets**. If this property is intact, then there is a *Hermitian equivalence* of polarity and root lattice structure across both the continuous and the discrete representations of an object.

Proposition 4.1.4. $\mathbf{A}_{\text{LENS}}$ lies in the same classifying stack as $\tilde{\Delta}:(\mathbf{L}^n \mathfrak{X})$ if and only if $\mathbf{D}_{\text{HAUS}}(\star:(-^p -^c)^\circ)$ does.

Remark This is to say that a space lies in the same classifying stack as its set of functions if and only if its compact Hausdorff realization is generated by its group of functions. For two rings, y_1, y_2 , the injection $y_1 \rightarrow y_2$ is a genuine (étale, Nisnevich, Zariski) morphisms if and only if both the source and target have identical codimension and polarity.

Proposition 4.1.5 If A and B lie in the same classifying stack as C if and only if there is a common pre-norm $\{\pi_k:A \cap B \cap C\}$.⁷

This last proposition means that a *classifying stack* (of topological/Kolmogorov spaces) over a set of stacks includes only stacks with some mutual geometric invariant. In our case, this is the Hausdorff dimension of the set of spaces, which corresponds to the fractal measure of a class of sites.

Proposition 4.2.1 For a map $K_1 \rightarrow K_2$ of Kolmogorov spaces, there is a split set of morphisms $\{s,c\}$ consisting of a stabilizer and a centralizer. This set is called the *inertial regulator* of its hereditary schemes.

Since Kolmogorov spaces are stable and regular (central with respect to a finite basis), all Hermitian isomorphisms between Kolmogorov spaces contain an inertial regulator. This is tantamount to saying that homotopy-bearing objects have pullbacks to an anima.

Proposition 4.2.2 All spaces with diagonals have entourages.

This statement immediately follows from the previous. Since Kolmogorov spaces have weakly chained presentations, they are all measurable at the boundary by an ε -chain of unspecified length.

Essentially, an $\mathcal{O}$ -isomorphism takes spaces of a property $\mathcal{O}$ and injects it into a motivic partner of property at most $\mathcal{O}^\#$, so that $\{\mathcal{O}, \mathcal{O}^\#\}$ forms an equivalence class of rings, and $\mathcal{O}_{\text{MOD}}$ becomes the

⁷ This is a restatement of the classical *Brown representability* and the *Brower fixed point theorems*.

respective class of $\{O, O^\# \}$ -modules. So, here we have an H-isomorphism of spaces and their adjoint Hermitian conjugates.

Property 4.2.3 Every H-space is a K-space, but not every K-space is an H-space.

The property of being Hermitian is stronger than the Kolmogorov property, which in this case we have chosen as complexity, as measured in the number of coprime distances between modules.

Theorem 4.2.4 An isomorphism of H-spaces is a homothetic transformation of compasses.

Proof We see that $2\mathfrak{S}^\dagger\mathbb{C}$ has the scalar quantity two, making $\mathbb{H}_{|\mathbb{C}}$ a $\mathbb{Z}/2$ -fold cover of $\mathbb{C}^\dagger$.

Property 4.2.5 $S+n|_S$ is a $(S-m)/m$ -fold cover over $S-m$.

Here we denote by S the relative “bigness” of a field; the naturals, in the reals, are strictly two-small, and three-small within the complex. $n|_S$ is the successor of S restricted to S , where n is the difference between n and $n|_S$. m is the successor to n . So, if we denote by the complex numbers 4, we have that the quaternions are 5, and the reals are 3. So, restricting to a real scalar of $\mathbb{C}$ gives $n=(4-3)=1$, and thus m is 2; so, $n=4-2$ maps to the *integers*, where the *natural numbers* are 1, and the set with zero and 1 are *zero*. This keeps $S+n|_S$ in a single O_{MOD} class, while $(S-m)/m$ -fold covers are in the O_{mod}^b class.

In the above example, $O_{mod}^b = \mathbb{Z}/2$, and $O_{MOD} = \{\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}\}$.

The function

$$\lceil \log_2 n \rceil = S_i$$

gives the site character. It is, respectively, one through three, and corresponds to either the étale, Nisnevich, or Zariski sites of a K- (respectively, H-)space. Its commutative spectrum is thus one of the following:

- $Sp_{\acute{e}t}(\Delta_i) \leftrightarrow \textit{formally \acute{e}tale}$
-
- $Sp_{Nis}(\mathbb{A}_\infty) \leftrightarrow \textit{formally Nisnevich}$
 - $Sp_{Zar}(\mathbb{E}_\infty) \leftrightarrow \textit{formally Zariski}$

and whence two commutative spectrum are encompassed by a common locus, they are compared using the δ_i -smallness operad. So, for a *formally étale slice flatly embedded* in a Zariski spacetime, we obtain the δ_2 -smallness, where $i=-m$, and where $\delta:\Delta$ is a property typified by simplicial complexes.

For the reverse immersion, we obtain δ_{-2} , and for $\delta=Scene$, one has $\partial Scene_{-2}$.

What we have seen so far is that our O_{MOD} is a very *easy*, if not *good topological invariant*! In fact, of Bott periodicity we can say that it is exerted by $\delta_{\pm 2}$ -cyclotomic trace maps.

$$\mathbf{Bott}_8 = \delta_{\pm 2};$$

this is a somewhat insightful consequence of Bott periodicity, that it acts through an adjoint spectral Θ^i - ∞ loop operator in the category of sites. In fact, $\log_2(\delta)$ is acting on the cycles through inertial regulation.

This is the result of the chapter’s final equivalence theorem

Theorem 4.3.0 $\log_2\{\{1,2\},\{3,4\},\{5,6,7,8\}\} \simeq \mathbf{Bott}_8 \simeq \mathcal{C}(S)_\infty$ yields a tri-cycle of co-skelata.

Proof Here, we have placed the relevant numerals into type-identified brackets, which relate the supremum of the subset to all other numbers in the co-class.

The three sets of dimensions are labeled, respectively:

- $\text{re}(\mathbb{H}), \mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1; \sup \mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^1 = \kappa$
- $\mathbb{C}\mathbb{P}^2, \mathbb{H}; \sup \mathbb{H} = \aleph_a$
- $\mathbb{O} \quad \sup \mathbb{O} = \aleph_{3+a}$

according to the field which is forced through the inclusion of the $\mathbb{S}_1$ -th dimension.

We see, $\inf(\sup:\mathbb{F}_i) \simeq \mathbb{S}_{\pm 1}$ yields κ , and so therefore κ is the inf-pole of the compass $\Omega_\kappa^{\aleph_{3+a}}$, which essentially provides a Lagrangian (Weil-Peterson path metric) minimization from $\mathbb{N}$ to $\mathbb{O}$ by “gluing” their poles together along an edge. Here, $\mathbb{F}_i$ is the class of all Kolmogorov-complete adic (*herein, Hermitian*) spaces in the relevant ± 2 -cocycle, starting at $\{3,4\} \simeq \aleph_a$.

Assume that the polarity is effectively, constantly, $\mathbb{b}^\pm$. Then, we have that

$$\{\mathbb{b}^{\pm \simeq \kappa} \mid 1 \leq i \leq 3\} \simeq \mathbf{Bott}_8\{2\} \in \mathcal{C}(S);$$

here we have defined $i:S_c \rightarrow S_c'$ to be a map to a more granular space, and it is thus the successor function as applied to the above formula.

Chapter 5 | Weakly Chained Spaces and Periodicity

To summarize the results of the previous session, a certain *boundary condition* (the Σ -condition) must be satisfied by $\mathbf{Top}^{\text{fl}}$ in order to obtain the (set-theoretic) difference of *stacks* which classify groupoids into homogeneous spaces.⁸ Thus, we make the necessary translation from talking about differentials and such to *thinking about* some sort of K -, or KO -structure over an elliptically fibred section of, say, an n -torus. Conrad Plaut mastered the art of this discussion.⁹

It is easier to realize, in some cases, a Boltzmann brain than a geometric representation for a perfectly smooth scheme of infinitary complexes. To say the least, the entropy over such a state is like a big *children's drawing*, or a game of *connect the dots*.

For Newtonian mechanics, this game is made deceptively simple, especially when using the modern tools of Naive homotopy theory.¹⁰ The specific tool of a *shape monad*, particularly of a *winding number*, $f\omega_\kappa$, characterizes in broad terms the number of “chambers” (greater strata), say, an electron’s spin state may occupy given a polarization scheme, $q^\pm$. For a monopole, we would imagine the differential would be taken over the Zariski site in order to obtain the “*genuine metric*” (at a point).

⁸ The *integral technique* (of infinitesimals) is remarkably similar to the work of supersymmetry being done by physicists who work on string theory.

⁹ See [W.C.]

¹⁰ Naive is not to be meant pejoratively

This enables us to envision that the *compactification* occurs at the *order of* (scale of) the étale site. Thus, a complex spinorial Hopf fibration receives a simple geodesic minimization when represented at the level of the finite-dimensional or *lower ranked* Hilbert space.

Clausen,¹¹ described étale descent as a sort of *telescopic process*, particularly with respect to some topological invariant, k , which *here* we have described as either a *transcendental ordinal* or a *log-shell variety*, for $\log_2(8)$. One such invariant that has strong ties, and we may regard as being very similar, is the polar structure, *in degree*, as measured by the second-order differential, which is taken from some projector of the membrane of which the Quillen fibrations are the target.

We can consider “undoing” a differential, say by writing $\partial\partial^{-1}\delta$, as an act of *retraction* to the base space of some fiber structure (say, a manifold, which is a particularly nice example of an orbifold), which preserves certain tautological invariants at the level of the *Planck scale* by a certain variety of *homothety*. In Plaut-specific notation, we might have

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \Omega_{\partial}^{\epsilon}$$

as something like a certain “twist” of infinitesimal characteristic. We create a simple graph by *coupling* the term $\bar{\epsilon}$ to a field $\mathfrak{K}$, thus creating a *locally constant sheaf* across each of the *smooth* and ϵ -distinct points along a boundary. In some sense, this is the canonical *Frobenius action* (of a universal open filter) on a constrained compass.

A question I might have is, how is this specific invariant, $\bar{\epsilon}$, related to the so-called “Gromov-Witten” invariant? It seems to me to be just like any other topological invariant, and so it too could be used for calculating differentials of degree two.

In any case, this is just a somewhat new coat of paint on an old tale – *calculus of variations*. I have introduced my own terminology – the so-called “supersite,”¹² to denote an eigenvector with dimension which acts upon an inertial body – the “sup” of a *supersite lattice*, which is “spectral” in its nature. We call the body the zero-object, and it is that which is not seen in calculus to be the denominator for any division map.

There is a partial link here to the Dirac delta function, which diverges at both zero and infinity. Oftentimes, in physics, “infinities” are treated as *errors* to be *corrected*, and, in some circles, *zeros* have come to be called into philosophical questioning as well. This is rather odd, because in the picture we are painting here, infinities, in the sense of Riehl, are the sort of *tame* structures to be working with. They are awfully convenient perhaps for certain tasks, like taking the derivative of a projection of stacks across sites.

¹¹ Reference unknown

¹² A somewhat precarious, and arguably ad-hoc construction

We see the connection between points as twisted fibers, and their induced metric is a torsor of some weighted value of a graded subfield. A *twistor* is technically an example of a *mod 2* construction, as it is a *two-fold covering* of $\mathbb{Z}$ by $\mathbb{Z}/2$. Precisely because two is just one of any of a given set of prime numbers, there are eigenstates determined by any of the other primes, such that we may set $\mathbb{Z}/p$ to be an ideal domain for outcomes of superposition equations.

This has implications for quantum communication, because for two or more entangled bodies with probabilities $\sqrt{p}$ of converging to an outcome of a spectral sequence, there is a trivially complete connection to the *good moduli space* of a pre-geometric quasiconformal variety. So, for p entangled channels, the multipartite connection has $\sqrt{p}^2!$ modes of entanglement!

The fields of today, such as the “*superreal*” (as constructed by Woodin), $\mathbb{SR}$, are not just novel abstractions to be idled with! They are a sort of *subfine* variation of the affine theory of the classical forces. They simply make second-order *corrections* to the operational locus of the traditional semiotically operable regimes. One can in fact find that there are an infinite number of computations to be made with any given data set, just as there are an infinite number of experiences to be manufactured from any given technology! So, much of the power of new number fields is that it gives us *control over manipulating data* (sometimes in a more profitable way).

For instance, eigenvectors such as *shear* and *grad* can be used to deform data in order to eliminate (or introduce certain *helpful*) statistical biases, some of which are obvious, and some of which are quite subtle.

If we look at the raw data of a situation, we will be blinded by disastrous statistical flaws, such as a lack of reliable sources on the publication date, lack of information about the *contextual circumstances regarding the events of that time*, or lack of additional information we might wish to obtain, but have to introduce various “fudge factors” to cook up.

The fact that there are different layers of *convolution* between different cross-products, which are used to obtain *simples*, and the simples themselves, causes a hefty deal of *confusion*. Whenever we look at a twisted topological space, we should look at what its perfectly flat counterpart is.

I digress. Let $\text{cd}(-)$ be the cohomological dimension of an affine $\mathbb{SR}$ -module, and let ι_γ be a shear transformation on $\text{cd}(-)$. We obtain, as the boundary manifold begins to curl, an increased density of *truth values* (at the level of sub-object identifiers) *per weight module*.

$$\iota_\gamma \tau \mathbb{B}^{-n} \propto \mathbf{T}_\epsilon$$

We relate the above formula to $\text{sup}(\text{cd}(-))$ by taking $\text{Hom}(\mathbf{T}_{\bar{\epsilon}}, \epsilon \times \epsilon)$ and assigning to each section of the diagonal $\epsilon \times \epsilon$ a unique path P_θ which consists of open balls of diameter $\leq \epsilon$.

Write $\text{Spec}(\kappa)$ for an $\bar{\epsilon}$ -condensed transcendental ordinal. Then, one has

$$\text{Hom}(\mathbf{T}_{\bar{\epsilon}}, \epsilon \times \epsilon) \Vdash e^2$$

for a small, open field extension e . We call, for a Hurewicz isomorphism,

$$f:(e \rightarrow e') \simeq \text{Map}(e, \text{Hom}(e, e')),$$

we call the retract f^{-1} a *supersite* if it is both clopen, and admits a torsion free subgroup $\mathbf{t}^{-1}$ such that

$$\mathbf{Hocol}_{\leftarrow} \mathbf{t}^{-1}(\mathbb{N}_v) = p$$

is preserved under pullback.

We find here, another connection with loop stacks, for if $\mathbf{L}^\infty \mathfrak{X} \simeq p$, then we say the stabilizer about $p \cup \{*\}$ has all automorphisms into its ambient space. This means, for some factor f , the result of multiplying fp is a *genuine isomorphism* (at the level of sites), of ε -chains. Thus, $p \cup \{*\}$ is a *transitive* (and multiplicative) *inner model*, which effectively makes it a commutative monoid. Thus, all maps $p \cup \{*\} \rightarrow \mathbf{L}^\infty \mathfrak{X} \cup \{*\}$ are *based* at topoi.

Anywyho, we say that an open map

$$\{*\} \xrightarrow{\bar{\varepsilon}}_{\varepsilon} \{\infty\}$$

is a *trace preserving map* (of cycles) if every epic of Serre fibrations is an injective Hurewicz isomorphism. Thus, the line bundle over $\{*\}_\Sigma$ is *tautological*, in the lax monoidal sense. We say the *period* of the map is n when $\text{cd}(\{\infty\})$ is n , and so also when the space is an n -dimensional Hilbert space. As we can see,

Proposition 5.1.1 All trace preserving maps are maps of weakly chained spaces.

Proof Fix a space S , and a simplicial complex $\tilde{\Delta}$. If, for every point in S there is a retract to a 0-cell, we say the space is *based*, and call such a point the initial object.

For any space S' with retracts to a geometric point, $\{*\}$, such a space contains an initial object, and is therefore, weakly chained of polarity $\bar{\varepsilon}$.

Proposition 5.1.2. $\{*\}$ is a supersite

Proof By the isomorphism with infinity, $\{*\}$ is transcendental over the natural numbers, and thus contains at least the reals.

In other words, $\{*\}$ has enough admissible monics to $\mathcal{C}(S)$.

Proposition 5.1.3 Looped spaces are weakly chained.

Follows immediately from the *trace preserving* mapping $\mathbf{L}^\infty \mathfrak{X} \cup \{*\} \rightarrow \mathbf{L}^\infty \mathfrak{X} \cup \{\tilde{\Delta}\}$.

Example 5.1.4 A mapping which is not trace preserving; let $dC_n \rightarrow \{*\}$ be a map of a degenerate cocycle to a pluripotent loop functor. The map does not preserve trace, as there are some epics which are not effective, and therefore are not properly surjective.

Thus, for $n > 1$, the maps fail to preserve trace.

Proposition 5.1.5 Maps between supercompact cardinals preserve trace.

Proof Let κ, ω be supercompact cardinals; then one has $\text{sup}(\mathbf{B} = \{\kappa, \omega\})$ is preserved, even if a new member, say, ω_0 is inserted into the set. This conversely also holds for $\text{inf}(\mathbf{B})$.

Conjecture 5.2.1 Trace-preserving maps are always quasi-coherent.

This is a result of the periodicity of trace-preserving maps remaining faithful, modulo a certain (small) prime number, the *log shell*. We also stake claim here that $\text{spec}(\kappa) \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \text{spec}(\omega)$ is a coherent or quasi-coherent (short) exact sequence of *spectra*.

If this conjecture holds, then automorphisms between display blocks, $\text{Aut}(\mathbf{B})$, are always trace-preserving, with maps ϕ_n constituting the forgetful portion of the sequence.

Conjecture 5.2.2 A map $\text{spec}(\kappa) \rightarrow \text{spec}(\omega)$ is always coherent if ω succeeds κ .

So, if ω is the completion of an open field κ , then an injection is strictly coherent, as injections into successors are always coherent in a dipolar compass. A series of maps $\phi_n \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \phi_n$ form an *effectively lensed* sub-display block. Because they forget coherency (for the most part), only quasi-coherency is guaranteed.

So, if the span of $\phi_n \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \phi_n$ is i , then the sequence is *i-truncated*, with respect to the category of commutative spectra. If, and only if this sequence is automorphic, and Hurewicz, then we have a genuinely coherent series.

Lemma 5.2.3 A series is genuinely coherent if and only if the inf-pole of a compass is preserved.

If there is a map $\Omega_-^* \rightarrow \Omega_-^{*'}$, such that $(-)$ and $(-')$ are distinct, then they are not necessarily homothetic, and therefore only quasi-coherency is guaranteed. A quasi-coherent lifting of compasses acts by rational R -modules, so that the inf-pole of a compass C_2 can be written $\underline{C}_2$, where by an underlined C we mean C^R . As a result, quasi-coherent transformations are C^R -epic at every infinitesimal place, and thus in this sense “smooth.” We have the canonical form

$$\underline{C}_N = \lim_{\leftarrow} C_i^R \rightarrow \Omega_i$$

defining the De Rham cohomology of a space of differential forms over a stack. Bear in mind that i is “really” an ε -chain consisting of a single simplex. Thus, it is a unique topological invariant characterizing a genus N space. Each path $\underline{C}_N \rightarrow \underline{C}_N$ represents a *similitude* of the fiber bundle over the relevant topological stack.

In the p -adic case, two *valuation rings* $R\Omega_p^*$ and $R\Omega_{p'}^*$ are necessarily *right homothetic*, since some transformation may act upon the last k digits of the compass to yield homogeneity mod q . Thus, it is the case that condensed mathematics often specializes in the adic regime. So, in some special sense, there are *more trace-preserving maps* in the p -adic case, which makes certain computations easier. Thus, we identify the torsor t as acting upon both of p, p' by a common moduli space, which is assumed to be good.

Finally, for a trace preserving map $K \rightarrow K'$, we say that it is *period preserving* if

$$\text{Lim}_{\leftarrow} \lceil \log_k(b) \rceil > R$$

for some even number b relatively coprime to either of p or p' . R is then the periodic number of the class of cocycles associated with a set of fibrations. As we have shown that trace preserving maps are quasi-coherent, it follows that so too are period preserving maps *at least* quasi-coherent.

Finally, we make the remark that for a compass with a successor, say Ω_p^κ , the successor shall be written as a *sup-pole*; i.e., assuming ω to succeed κ , we write Ω_p^ω , and not, say Ω_{p+1}^κ . This maintains the integrity of the underlying displays, so as to minimize the number of *i-truncated* maps of the extension, and thus to minimize the periodic number of the spectrum.